

Health promoting lifestyle in educational setting: an intervention study in the universities

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ABSTRACT

The "health promoting universities" strategy has gained popularity and a presence in the higher education system, particularly in universities. It is imperative for higher education establishments to prioritize the promotion of health within their student body and academic community. By safeguarding and boosting students' wellbeing, a strategy centered on encouraging healthy lifestyles has the potential to boost the university's contribution to health improvement and offer significant value to the community. Universities have the power to improve health promotion through community service and to make policies in this area through research and teaching. In order to investigate student behavior in relation to the standard aspects of the health-promoting lifestyle profile, this project will undertake an intervention study involving 150 students with the goal of promoting a healthy lifestyle. A pre-test and post-test control group design was employed in this investigation. The health-promoting lifestyle standard profile II questionnaire was the research instrument, and descriptive statistics and inference were employed for analysis at the .05 significant level. The outcomes demonstrated a noteworthy impact on the implemented measures. This study's findings indicated that interventions in learning environments successfully raised student behavior linked to a healthy lifestyle and its components.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The university is the highest educational institution, where the education system for students is implemented with an andragogical approach. The andragogy approach is a learning process that involves adults in the structure and learning experience. Conditions and learning experiences at universities tend to be more complex than educational institutions at lower levels because they have to consider many external and internal aspects and factors in the learning process [1]. One of the things that must be considered in university life is a health policy for the entire campus community. Health issues have long been a concern among higher education institutions, including health promotion among the campus community. This health promotion-based approach can potentially increase the university's contribution to improving the health of its population [2]. Universities can do many things to promote and protect the health of students and the entire academic community [3]. This must be done to create a work environment, learning, and education conducive to health. Furthermore, this strategy is also expected to contribute to the surrounding environment, help promote health in teaching and research, and also become a resource for public health in general. However, this strategy needs to be

implemented properly. The challenge is developing and building a healthy campus that can realize all of these aspects [4]–[6]. Enthusiasm and interest in the concept of a "health-promoting university" are quite large in line with the demands and expectations regarding improving public health in the campus environment [7]. Health promoting universities is a project supported by World Health Organization (WHO), which is studied based on conceptual, field experience, and a framework for action. In 2000, all living settings and social activities in the city, school, workplace, and home environment must provide greater opportunities to promote health [8]. However, in real conditions, especially in Indonesia, awareness and participation in promoting health still need to be improved. This is indicated by the high rate of sedentary behavior and low participation rate in sports/physical activity [9]. This condition results in a high risk of hypokinetic diseases (53% heart disease and stroke). Indonesia was even ranked 9th in the world for diabetes in 2010 and is predicted to rise to 6th in 2030 [10]. The same condition occurs in the university environment. Several conditions of health problems occur not only for physical health but also for mental health. Some students experience weight gain to the point of obesity, and around 24.9% of students experience anxiety [11]. Unhealthy lifestyles and eating patterns cause negative emotions and are risk factors for eating disorders and excessive weight gain [12]–[14]. The relationship between mental health and obesity is very complex, based on a 2010 systematic review finding that people who experience depression have a 58% increased risk of becoming obese [15].

To overcome these conditions and problems, it is necessary to carry out strategies and solutions. One is by researching the area of building a healthy campus: health-promoting lifestyle in the universities, which focuses on increasing health promotion in the campus environment. Health promotion in the university environment can be carried out with several strategies, including making policies to protect health and improve the welfare of the campus community [16]. Another strategy is through teaching and research processes, as well as conducting socialization and community service related to health [17]. This research aims to explore, visualize, develop, and promote a healthy lifestyle by conducting an intervention study to assess the health-related behavior of the community in the campus environment to create a "healthy campus" and "health promoting universities".

2. LITERATUR REVIEW

There has been a lot of research conducted in the field of health science studies which is linked to the world of education. Especially in the last two decades, there has been a rapid increase in evaluating and designing research related to health promotion through physical activity tests [18], [19]. This has become a supporting system for health institutions and organizations to produce evidence-based physical activity recommendations that are used as a medium to promote a healthy and active lifestyle throughout life [19], [20]. This research makes a significant contribution to public health, especially in managing and changing health behavior. The world of education is also a strategic setting to facilitate health promotion. through educational and learning settings, the transfer of knowledge regarding the importance of an active lifestyle is effective in helping to improve the level of public health. In various countries, guidelines have been created to improve physical activity and health. These guidelines provide recommendations for adults to carry out moderate to high-intensity physical activity with a duration of between 150-300 minutes and with a frequency of at least 2 times a week [21]. This recommendation was made in the context of preventive and curative efforts to overcome health problems caused by lack of movement or non-infectious diseases. Several research results state that adults who are sedentary and do not carry out physical activity according to recommendations are at increased risk of developing non-communicable diseases (for example type 2 diabetes and heart disease) and may be the main cause of death [22].

Overall, innovative interventions are needed to encourage people to be physically active on a regular and sustainable basis. An integrative approach to promoting physical activity and a health-promoting lifestyle is a concept that can be effectively implemented in education and learning settings so that it becomes a habit. This health promotion activity focuses on involving participants in continuous physical activity, with moderate to vigorous intensity, carried out for a short duration but done as often as possible. Possible activities include walking from the parking lot to the classroom or office building, squatting and standing while waiting in line, standing while teaching or doing work, or climbing stairs when going to the room [23]. Health promotion activities in educational settings at universities are supported by WHO. Health promoting universities is a project supported by WHO which is studied based on conceptual, field experience, and framework for action. During the year 2000, all settings of people's lives and social activities in cities, schools, workplaces, and home environments, must provide greater opportunities to promote health (WHO Europe Copenhagen, 1998). Schools are identified as ideal places for physical activity and health promotion. Health promotion and an active lifestyle can be a preventive and curative source for non-infectious disease problems such as obesity, high blood pressure, heart disease, and so on. educational settings, especially in universities have access to the majority of adolescents, adequate facilities, and qualified personnel to achieve

effective results [24]. Many school-based interventions are effective in increasing physical activity and preventing obesity [25], [26]. In comparison, evidence on the effectiveness of school-based interventions targeting adolescents found that school-based interventions were twice as successful as interventions targeting adolescents in regular social settings [14], [25], [27]. The challenge of achieving health behavior change has prompted the exploration of new and interesting intervention strategies.

3. METHOD

3.1. Research design

This research was quasi-experimental with a pretest–posttest control group design. The study's statistical population consisted of students from the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. The research was conducted for four months. The research location that is affordable and most likely to be measured is the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. Following the research objectives, explore, visualize, develop, and promote a healthy lifestyle.

3.2. Sampling

The subjects in this study were 150 students at the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. By comparing the means of two separate groups with a 95% confidence interval and a significance level of .05, the sample size was calculated using the sample size formula. Each group's total number of samples had a sample size of $n=75$. We employed a multistage random sampling strategy in this investigation. Two groups were chosen after a list of all faculties was created. The control group and the intervention group. The samples for the intervention and control groups were chosen at random. According to the student's medical record, there was no physical or mental illness that met the study's inclusion criteria. Students with medical or mental illnesses, as well as those who declined to continue participating in the study and filled out questionnaires, were excluded from the study. Following the justification of the project's sampling methodology, the following stage involves obtaining written consent, establishing the project's aim, and guaranteeing information confidentiality before initiating the study. In both groups, questionnaires were filled out and collected together with the demographic data.

3.3. Method

Before the intervention was carried out, the researcher gave informed consent to the participants as a sign of agreement that the sample was willing to voluntarily become participants in this research. This research was carried out by providing health promotion interventions to the campus community which were carried out by the research team for all treatment groups 2 times a week, while the control group did not receive any intervention. The intervention carried out was counseling, providing materials, and practicing physical activity directly to the treatment group. Both sample groups underwent a pre-test before the intervention and a post-test after the intervention. The intervention program consists of 16 training sessions for 45 to 60 min in $n=75$ groups using methods of short lectures, group discussions, questions, and answers, role-playing, and training materials, including instructional booklets, posters, pamphlets, progressive muscle relaxation training audio, physical activity, and nutrition.

3.4. Data collection

Data collection in this study used the health-promoting lifestyle standard profile II questionnaire to examine student behavior related to health promoting lifestyle and its dimensions. The standard health-promoting lifestyle questionnaire, which has six dimensions-spiritual growth (11 items), health responsibility (13 items), interpersonal researcher relationships (7 items), stress management (6 items), physical activity (8 items), and nutrition (7 items) [28]. The validity and reliability of this tool have been substantiated by numerous studies. A training regimen was created and put into action for the intervention group. Encouraging factors, attitudes, and subjective norms are all included in interventions pertaining to lifestyle aspects.

3.5. Data analysis

Using inferential statistical tests, the data collected following the intervention were examined using IBM SPSS version 20 (International Business Machines Corporation (IBM), New York, United States). The inference analysis used in this research is the independent sample t-test to test differences in each dimension of health promoting lifestyle between the intervention group and the control group.

4. RESULTS

The results of data analysis using a paired sample t-test stated that the intervention carried out in an educational setting affected student behavior related to health promoting lifestyle ($P 0.001$). In detail, the differences in each dimension of health promoting lifestyle between the intervention group and the control

group are described in Table 1. Based on Table 1, it can be explained that there are 6-dimensional items that build a health promoting lifestyle that is compared between the intervention and control groups. In addition, there are also the results of the overall analysis of the health promoting lifestyle variables in the intervention group and the control group. From the results of data analysis using the independent sample t-test, it is known that there are significant differences in the dimensions of health responsibility (p 0.001b), physical activity (p 0.001b), nutrition (p 0.003), spiritual growth (p 0.001), interpersonal relations (p 0.001), and stress management (p 0.002). Based on the average value obtained, it can be stated that the effect of educational setting intervention in the intervention group is better than the control group. The analysis results also stated that overall, the behavior related to the health promoting lifestyle of students in the intervention group was better than students in the control group (p 0.001).

Table 1. Independent sample t-test of health-promoting lifestyle and its dimensions in the control and intervention groups

Dimensions of health-promoting lifestyle profile	Mean ± standard deviation (SD)		Significance
	Intervention	Control group	
Health responsibility	25.04±5.09	21.36±4.89	0.001
Physical activity	16.49±4.28	14.41±4.95	0.001
Nutrition	26.24±4.21	22.38±4.30	0.003
Spiritual growth	27.59±3.31	23.30±4.02	0.001
interpersonal relations	26.23±4.31	24.36±3.99	0.001
Stress management	18.44±4.78	17.26±3.79	0.002
Overall	140.03±21.67	123.07±25.94	0.001

5. DISCUSSION

In general, the study's results stated that the health promotion behavior of students' lifestyles increased positively after being given intervention in an educational setting [29]. The effect of this intervention can also be supported based on behavioral change theories by increasing self-efficacy and self-confidence [30], also strengthening individual factors which are determining factors in improving the quality of lifestyle [31]. These factors include beliefs, values, perceptions, behavior patterns, and norms that contribute to quality improvement and health promotion for each individual [32]. Given that health promotion interventions using a behavioral approach seek to change individuals' behavior and encourage them to adopt a healthier lifestyle [33]. Therefore it can be concluded that education related to health promotion by influencing decision-making related to health can change individual behavior related to health [34], [35]. A healthy lifestyle is a valuable resource that reduces and prevents non-infectious diseases and their complications [36]. Based on the results of the research above, interventions carried out in educational settings influenced the healthy lifestyle behavior of the intervention group, this is in line with the results of research which stated that interventions through the educational process could increase the participants' healthy lifestyle scores [37], [38]. In another study, it was also stated that the average score of behavior in health promotion in female participants increased after 3 months of intervention [39]. These findings are also consistent with the results of studies that found health promotion interventions lead to increased attitudes toward health-related behaviors, improved skills, and healthy living behaviors [2], [40].

6. CONCLUSION

According to the study's findings, health-related behaviors and lifestyles, in all of their facets, can be increased and promoted through educational interventions in health promotion. Thus, interventions in health education settings, nutrition, environment modification, lifestyle adjustment, and behavior modification can all help to enhance population health behavior. As per the study's findings, the concept of self-efficacy is effectively employed in the implementation of health-promoting lifestyle in educational settings to encourage the adoption and adherence to healthy lifestyle activities. This is particularly successful in promoting a healthy lifestyle and promotes changes in healthy lifestyle behavior as well as the capacity to promote health literacy initiatives.

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